

SENSORY AND SUSTAINABLE STRATEGIES IN THE METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Today, design implies not only compliance with product technical-functional requirements but also with increasingly broader cultural demands concerning humans and the environment: respectively sensory attributes and environmental requirements.

The various disciplines involved have recently made considerable progress, by developing tools and methods that, interconnected and also with the development of neurosciences, are able to furnish increasingly realistic, scientific and objective explanations as to how we perceive the world. The paper presents an innovative approach, the ICS (Innovation, Comprehension, Sustainability) method and the correlated tools, which in some case have been patented by the Politecnico di Torino research group. In this way, by adopting the ICS method, the theoretical and scientific innovations should be translated into strategic instruments dedicated to large, small and medium enterprises.

Moreover, use of the ICS method is illustrated by presenting two case studies, the car seats concepts and the chocolate bar packaging, where the analysis is concentrated on sensory perception, in particular by using the Eye-tracking and Sensotact® tools.

Keywords: Design project, materials and products, sensory and sustainable profile.

EXPRESSIVE-SENSORY PERCEPTION OF MATERIALS AND PRODUCTS

In the current continuous innovation process in materials research, increasing attention is dedicated not only to environmental issues but also to the question of the perception of materials whose expressive-sensory properties, sought after or enhanced, acquire increasing importance. Increasing

consideration is given to the ways in which humans perceive matter and evaluate its experience. Consequently, this issue must be addressed not only with great sensitivity but also with rigor and a scientific approach of interdisciplinary scope, i.e. able to take into account, simultaneously, the various disciplines (physics, acoustics, ergonomics, sustainability, etc.) that may be involved and play an active role in designing the product and service (Rognoli and Levi, 2011). The design process must define the traditional capabilities of a material/product, by interpreting not only its technical or environmental requirements along its life cycle, but above all, by the interpretation and satisfaction of its sensory perception that should become a new element able to influence the project. Although our senses are discrete and discontinuous, our perception of the world is global and continuous. Even if in a specific context, we have the sensation of perceiving an environment and its characteristics in a continuous time frame, our eyes focus only on discrete elements in the direction we are looking, while most of our visual process is blind (Kosslyn, 1994; Muller and Rabbitt, 1989; Casco, Petrosini and Oliveri, 2007). We do not see with our eyes but through a complex cerebral process that fills in space-time voids with credible hypotheses based on experience, not on how the world is, but how it should be (Baldwin, 2003). Similarly, when studying an object, we do not analyse the entire object but only those few significant elements that comply with our hypotheses of reality (Farah M.J., 2000; Johnson-Laird, 1993). It is these significant elements that influence the design process.

As a result, according to the most advanced theories of design culture, the most suitable materials to construct the product must already be selected in the meta-project phase, which is consequently broadened and filled with new meanings. Consequently, materials have an acknowledged weight in the project as they support its technical functionality and, at the same

time, create its “personality” (Lerma and De Giorgi, 2011).

Therefore, it is necessary to formulate an objective method of parametric evaluation and measurement of the perceptual-sensory aspects of materials (and of products and services) which, interfacing with environmental requirements, is able to support the development of the project (Lerma, De Giorgi and Allione, 2011).

AFFECTIVE ASPECTS AND COGNITIVE PROCESSES

If, on one side, aspects of sensorial perception have a predominant role for this type of analysis, on the other side, we cannot underestimate the influence of the relationship between affective aspects and cognitive processes involved in the use of any object.

Among the models in the cognitivist field that accept the significance of affective aspects is that proposed by Van Raaij (1984). This author divides the affective reaction into two phases: a primary and a secondary phase, following the cognitive phase. When the level of primary emotion is consistent, the cognitive-based critical quality decreases, reducing the level of involvement and identification, but imprinting states of emotion in the memory (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Van Raaij model

The constructed model involves a reaction divided into three stages:

- 1) A primary affective impression, which at an irrational level, creates a general positive or negative reaction. If the emotion is excessive, it will inhibit the subsequent levels.
- 2) A cognitive stage in which interpretation occurs.
- 3) A third and final affective phase in which subject makes the final judgment due to closer examination of the first impression during the cognitive phase.

As much as the first affective phase is characterised by a holistic structure and leads to evaluations of an oppositional nature (I like it / I don't like it), we must attribute to the second phase greater complexity and therefore the need for taxonomisation of the different types of emotion and the type of influence on a behavioural level that each of these can provoke. Interpreting a text or a situation in conditions of heightened primary emotion can reduce the amount of information that people are able to process simultaneously (Sanbonmatsu, Kardes, 1988). On this research trend, a next step of Van Raaij's model leads to the identification that, through high emotional impact, almost complete inhibition of the cognitive process can be produced. By this, it can be said that adapting to a particularly pathemic situation can only occur following a recursive process which heightens the threshold of resistance to affective factors.

The designer interacts with emotions in six different ways:

- 1) he produces through the form an aesthetic attraction that draws attention, creates the desire to possess or use the object and produces a positive state of mind towards its use;
- 2) he creates an interface that can also be used in conditions of heightened emotion, which should therefore be clear, intuitive and cognitively manageable, even when certain situations reduce the processing capacities of the user;
- 3) he induces, clearly through warnings and the very structure of the interface, states of alert and attention to critical and potentially dangerous elements in the usage process;
- 4) he produces interfaces that do not overburden the cognitive system so as not to invoke frustrating, demotivating and pernicious experiences in the user;
- 5) he designs a path of interaction which facilitates learning and which, intuitively, helps the user not to make errors and to produce the right approach with the product and its use;
- 6) he designs objects and situations that do not deceive the user, by sending false promises of results, but which, though safeguarding

aesthetics, transmit the right content and values (Vannoni, 2009).

BACKGROUNDS

THE SENSORY AND ENVIRONMENTAL DIMENSIONS

Nowadays, when choosing any type of product, the consumer is involved in a sensory experience that perceives characteristics such as softness, aroma, sound, shape and colour no longer as secondary elements in relation to function, but more as complementary aspects able to facilitate its use.

Therefore, industries now endow their products with a sensorial dimension in order to meet consumers' new demands in terms of handling, touching and feeling them on their skin. Materials, and products made of these, communicate with all our senses, furnishing knowledge of the multi-sensory world and implying a synesthetic perception comprising tactile, visual, auditory, olfactory and gustative sensations (Riccò, 1999). Each perception may have a twofold quality. There is, in fact, a tactility of sight or even auditory vision. Colours may be simply cold or warm but also light or heavy. A sound may be dull or piercing while at the same time evoking a sensation of freshness. Communication between object and subject is becoming increasingly synesthetic, involving a greater number of the senses, particularly touch, in addition to sight. Attentive selection in the design phase of materials able to create new tactile sensations, such as particular elastomers and polymers, that make surfaces soft or pliant, are able, in any case, to communicate something that is becoming ever more important to the user. The vibration of a mobile phone is also a way of communicating.

Therefore, industries are increasingly attentive to a product's sensory attributes, whether it is a car or a lipstick.

Selection of the material and of its perceptual dimensions is now fundamental in determining its market positioning: sensory qualities can be designed and the definition of these represents a major field of action. Furthermore the world of materials libraries has also shown an increasing interest in sensory aspects in recent years.

At the same time, eco-compatibility has now become an essential aspect of all products, materials, semi-finished products and services (Ashby, 2009). This demand can be considered as cross-industry in that it

involves the suppliers of products or services (required ever more frequently to demonstrate commitment to the environment through certification), the person (raising awareness of the need for a more virtuous environmental behaviour) and, primarily, the designer who, when devising the product/service, has a significant opportunity to determine, at source, the low environmental impact of the product/service throughout its life cycle (Manzini and Vezzoli, 1998; Tamborrini, 2009).

STATE OF THE ART OF THE SENSORY EVALUATION

Sensory evaluation is the scientific discipline used to evoke, measure, analyse and interpret the sensations that may be perceived by the senses of sight, smell, taste, touch and hearing (Melgaard, Civille and Carr, 2007). Sensory science is adopted in order to improve the sensory quality of different products: from fabrics to the environment, from fashion to cosmetics, from advertising to means of transport (Pagliarini, 2002). The key issue for sensory science is to connect the product with the person, making them aware of the great amount of chemical and physical information about a product by using one or various senses at the same time. This entails the acquisition of in-depth knowledge regarding the interactions between materials/products and the human mind, which changes with time and according to context.

Therefore, the concept of "affordance" (Gibson, 1979; Norman, 1997), i.e. the ability to perceive and use the actionable properties perceived through specific signs of an object, has become essential. For example, a chair expresses its affordance when it communicates perceptible signs that allow a person to categorise it as something to sit on and to use it for this purpose. Affordance is, therefore, implicit in certain specific characteristics of the object when these are perceived and understood by a person. Similarly, other objects may also contain these "perceptiles" that invite use of the object for a parallel or secondary purpose (for example, for sitting: a wall, a crate, a staircase may invite use of these in their secondary functions). Current sensory evaluations comprise pre-defined, standardised measurement techniques used both by industry and research centres. The techniques used to carry out sensory evaluations must be reliable (reproducibility in statistical terms when trials are

carried out in a suitable way); pertinent (i.e. consistent with the final goal compared with measurements taken using technical instruments) and substantial (considering that the human brain has an incredible capacity to correct evaluations with regard to interference; what is complex in chemistry and physics is often simple for the human eye or nose). There are two main approaches of sensory evaluation: analytical and hedonistic. The analytical approach includes discrimination and descriptive methods that define, respectively, any difference between the products and the degree of that difference (how intense a yellow colour is, how soft a fabric is, how dark a suit is, to what extent and how the fabric reflects light). The hedonistic approach establishes which products are preferred by consumers.

The analytical methods require “use” of a qualified sensory panel consisting of persons trained to detect and record sensory perceptions in standard product test conditions. Similarly to a measurement instrument, trained assessors provide accurate, reproducible results.

Both methods should be adopted, but if the hedonistic approach is implemented in the ICS method, a further analysis step is an in-depth evaluation of both “weak signals” and of the “evoked response” by recurring at the result of a sensory workshop. Specifically, the term “sensory workshop” has been coined to break away from the common concept of “focus group” in order to exalt the peculiar aspects of in-depth analysis and search for “weak signals” that characterise the new method.

In a context in which “classical” research and market analysis have reached saturation point at conceptual level, companies have expressed a need for innovative methods and instruments able to reproduce reactions to products and services: attention to sensory aspects combined with the use of innovative and so far unknown instruments has proved to be a potential solution to this need, an offshoot of

knowledge and strategies in which the “human factor” (Germak, 2008) becomes a core element of each approach to the product.

AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF BOTH SENSORY AND SUSTAINABILITY PROFILES: THE ICS METHOD

The ICS (Innovation, Comprehension, Sustainability) method is based on breaking down any product or service into a series of sensory attributes based on the assumption that suitable sensory composition also generates a harmonic system able to effectively convey one or more meanings (Figure 2).

This method is aimed at reaching four main goals:

- the innovative potential of sensory characteristics (definition of new sensory identities, optimisation of further sensory aspects, recreation of sensory identities);
- analysis of sensory attributes (identification of the characteristics of the single perceptiles, understanding of the evoked response);
- evaluation of the level of stimulation of a specific sense, sensory-semantic coherence of a product/service, cognitive overload;
- the identification of the eco-compatibility attributes and the evaluation of the perception of these green attributes, i.e. the study of the interactions and reciprocal relations between environmental sustainability and the sensory attributes of a material object or service.

Today, the single perceptiles and their integration have become phenomena to be analysed scientifically and objectively in order to induce strategic awareness in the designer and in whoever produces and sells specific products and services. The conceived method looks beyond the objects and starts by categorising the single materials and the “absolute” perceptiles that these produce.

The work carried out at MATto, the Materials Library

Figure 2. Diagram of ICS method

of the Politecnico di Torino, represents the basis of this process but is also integrated with qualitative analysis skills and new instruments that allow the end user to undertake a cognitive journey through the world of innovative materials and their perceptive characteristics and qualities (Lerma and De Giorgi, 2011).

With ICS method it is possible to define the indication lines of the product innovation, based on the identification of the main perceptiles and their integration with a low environmental profile.

TOOLS ADOPTED IN THE ICS METHOD

The integration for each sense of specific tools that provide objective data comparable to the structuring in thought of mental models, attitudes, judgment and decisional processes, is a way of exploring the minds of potential categories of purchasers in order to produce strategically relevant results able to guide companies towards the best decisions.

Available tools include Sensotact®, SuonBe and Eye-tracking which can be used individually or in an integrated way.

Sensotact® is the first universal reference instrument for the tactile characterisation of materials, created at the Renault TechnoCentre. The use of this instrument is intended to facilitate exchanges between entities, avoiding misunderstandings, creating a tactile reference to be promoted as a universal language. Sensotact® is a case containing 10 descriptors and 50 references that interact to describe the tactile attributes of a product. The Sensotact® method proposes breakdown of the sense of touch into 10 descriptors associated with three movements: static contact, orthogonal movement and tangential movement.

SounBe®, developed by the team and patented by Politecnico di Torino (De Giorgi, Astolfi, Buiatti, Lerma, Arato and Dal Palù, 2011), is a tool for qualitative and descriptive acoustic evaluation of materials through standardised stimulation of materials and objects. SounBe® is an instrument that evolves.

The tool is based on three essential elements that influence the nature of sound: the type of material used, its shape and the gestures adopted (by whoever is manipulating the material). The tool is combined with a specifically studied method that permits univocal stimulation of the materials in all their various

combinations and shapes. The materials and the sound they produce are then evaluated by groups of tasters (panel of persons trained in evaluating the acoustic behaviour of materials) who, using specific adjectives, define and describe the sounds produced by the materials stimulated. This inquiry will be carried out according to a statistical procedure through which those most applicable to the sound produced will be selected from a group of attributes. According to the adjective selected by the designer for the sound of the product (dull, strident, piercing, thin, etc.), it will be possible to select the most suitable materials and forms of presentation according to the gestures corresponding to the sounds to be obtained.

Also, in carrying out any cognitive task, SounBe® could permit evaluation of the suitability, the mental work load, the stimulus of attentive processes that a specific sound may stimulate in the user when carrying out a task (for example using virtual interfaces).

Finally Eye-tracking is a hi-tech instrument for recording and analysing the user's eye movements during exploration, for example, of a website or while observing an object. It is designed to study the behaviour of the human eye as it reads an image or a product. In Eye-tracking, sensors are used to record the reflection of a band of infrared rays projected on the pupil. As this signal changes according to the position of the pupil (and therefore the gaze direction), recording and analysing eye movements makes it possible to establish the precise point and for how long the user looks at a specific object. Analysing what an individual observes or ignores when deciding to consider a certain product provides crucial information regarding the ability of the product/interface/object to attract and maintain or distract the observer's attention.

In effect, it is possible to deduce the user's level of attention to what is being observed, how the user processes the information contained in a page or advert, strategies and any possible problems that may be encountered during these activities.

As a corollary to sensory analysis, the ICS method also takes account of the analysis of the eco-compatibility level of existing products, meta-project concept, definitive projects and prototypes. This analysis is intended not only to verify the level of eco-compatibility but also to provide design suggestions

with regard to how to improve the ecological footprint of the studied object and how to increase the perception of its eco-compatibility profile.

To measure the degree of compliance with environmental requirements, several Ecotools have been developed and are now widely used, such as checklists often based on guidelines and best practices, LCA assessment, as indicated in the ISO procedure, or Simplified LCA methods that generally adopt qualitative and quantitative parameters for evaluation.

Systems of self-declaration or environmental certification that a company may adopt “voluntarily” to demonstrate that its product offers better environmental performance are based on these methods able to assess life cycle product performances. However, despite their fundamental contribution, SMEs have difficulty in applying these methodologies of environmental assessment as they frequently involve expensive analyses and procedures. As a result three different levels of evaluation are possible in the proposed ICS method: an environmental profiling of materials and production processes involved up to gate; a simplified LCA based on assessment of the quantitative and qualitative parameters of the life cycle of existing products or meta-project concept; a complete quantitative LCA of existing products or prototypes nearing production.

QUALITATIVE AND ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF THE ICS METHOD

It is important to emphasise that the data resulting from the tools alone are not sufficient in order to understand a phenomenon in its entirety. We must remember that there is a huge difference between what we perceive through a sense and what, on the other hand, is processed by our brain. For this reason, the ICS method focuses on integrating analytical and qualitative techniques with the sensorial analysis tools that are currently available. These techniques are aimed at identifying emotive levels and their relationship with cognitive aspects, of “weak signals”

inherent in the perception of any interface and of new creative ideas that grow from the requirements of the users themselves, representing a valid tool for confirming or disproving data resulting from the tools used for the analysis.

In that sense, the analysis steps may be summarized into a path, which can be broken down into the following stages (Figure 3):

- desk analysis, i.e. a technique that consists of the decomposition into elements of one or more objects with the aim of identifying, through comparative grids, the salient and innovative aspects of a specific field.
- Positioning of the product on the FBC grid, which allows for investigation of the phenomenon of involvement, including responses of an emotive, cognitive and behavioral nature. Through an empirical analysis of consumer behavior, Vaughn and Berger identify the correlations between the product categories, the level of involvement and the predominant decision-making method of consumption (Vaughn and Berger).
- Qualitative sessions, i.e. a method, which allows for the development of creativity. It involves the use of creative techniques, along with various stimuli and tests. In particular, it is based upon two specific stages of development: the first is specifically divergent, in that it gives free rein to the imagination; the second is convergent where ideas produced in the first stage are brought back to an applicable form.
- Questionnaires: the individuals involved express, through different levels of investigation, judgments and inclinations on different aspects of interest. This is done by completing value scales, but also through closed and open questions or by integrating stylised graphics into the object in question.
- Tracking programme with tools (Sensotact®, SounBe® and Eye-tracking): this allows for the

ICS METHOD - MAIN STEPS

Figure 3. The main steps of the method ICS

analysis to be oriented towards objective and quantifiable data, affording the study the scientific investigations required for its completion.

- Semantic differentials. This is a particular type of scale, which aims at assessing the meaning that certain facts and specific concepts represent for the individuals interviewed. The ‘oppositions’ that arise within the judgments highlight the dichotomous aspects of the study domain and become focal points to be investigated.

These techniques, therefore, fulfill the aspects of innovation and understanding of the ICS method which, alongside the analyses of eco-sustainability and use of sensorial tools, contribute to the comprehensive nature of the results.

In the next paragraphs are illustrated two case studies that better explain the advantages by the adoption of the ICS method.

CASE STUDY 1: ANALYSIS OF THE CAR SEATS CONCEPTS

This paragraph illustrates a case study, the car seats concepts, paying attention not to their environmental performance, but to their sensory perception, particularly by using the Eye-tracking and Sensotact® tools (Lerma and De Giorgi, 2011): specifically, the aim of this case study is to integrate the two tools so as to test their strengths and weaknesses.

More specifically, we wish to verify, with Eye-tracking, whether the results obtained by the method of sensorial analysis of materials (with the aid of the Sensotact®), correspond or otherwise to what is perceived by the user “at first sight” (Figure 4). The expectation is for the considerations made thus far and the results of the tests performed to be validated.

In this case study the ICS method is adopted by following the scheme into figure 5 (Figure 5).

Through the use of this instrument, in other words, we attempt to understand and assess whether the expressiveness of a product (in the case study considered, a car seat upholstered in different fabrics) has any effect on the emotions experienced by an individual and whether that emotion is able to influence the individual’s behaviour, but above all what effect it has on the comprehension of the real tactile characteristics of the product.

The test was carried out on the concepts of car seats, developed by students in the third year of the degree program in Industrial Design, during the ReSeat in collaboration with the Fiat Research Center: the goal was to identify the upholstery proposals that were most attractive to the user-observer.

To proceed with the sensorial analysis of these concepts it was necessary, first of all, to select the potential fabrics to evaluate, among those available in

Figure 4. The Sensotact® tool and an example of the analysis with the Sensotact® tool on two fabrics catalogued in MATto.

the MATto.

The objective was then to analyse, compare and assess the concepts, examined in their sensorial aspects, with a view to furnishing an aid to the designers in the choice of the upholstery to use.

Concept pictures, or renderings, of the seats were developed, rather than real seats or prototypes, because the goal of the experiment was to assess the usefulness of an instrument like Eye-tracking during

ANALYSIS OF THE CAR SEAT CONCEPTS

Figure 5. Scheme of the adoption of ICS method into the car seat concepts analysis.

the design stages: by making the analyses on virtual models rather than on real models or prototypes this ensured a saving of resources and costs.

The analyses with Eye-tracking were performed with the instrument Tobii T120, which looks like a normal 17" monitor and provides a recording without any contact with the subject's eyes and does not require the use of a head-mounted device.

THE METHOD USED TO PERFORM THE ANALYSIS ON THE CAR SEATS CONCEPTS

To perform these analyses it was necessary to produce different images of the seat concepts to show to the viewers. Two versions of the car seats were designed: single fabric version, two fabric version. These images were shown to the viewers in random sequence, and also differed from individual to individual, and were displayed on the screen for 10 seconds in order to prevent the individuals from being influenced in their observations by the vicinity of images with fabrics of similar colours.

A small group of volunteers, consisting of 14 people; 5 men and 9 women aged between 22 and 40, performed the analysis. The individuals were then split up according to sex, age, educational level and type of driver.

In order to allow for evaluation of the data resulting from the analyses made with Eye-tracking, it was necessary to have the individual compile a semantic differential evaluation.

The semantic differential consists of a set of bipolar adjectives (having opposite meanings) to be assessed by the subject on a Lickert scale with 5 or 7 points, placed on the opposite ends of the scale. Assessment of 7 adjectives (and their opposites) was proposed for the definition of the fabrics selected, i.e. 7 adjective pairs. To prevent an effect of deconcentration, the positive and negative polarities were placed at random, on the right or left of the scale. In addition, according to the revision of the semantic differential proposed by Ricci (1980), we found it advisable to eliminate the ambiguity of the zero point (obtaining a scale with 6 passages) and to take account of individual variability.

Each individual made a semantic differential appraisal for each image, on a scale of 1 to 6, in which 1 was the worst case (very negative) and 6 the ideal case (very positive).

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

We analysed the gaze plots, heat maps and gaze replays obtained following the tests with the Tobii device. The results, in our analyses, were then matched to the results deriving from the semantic differential appraisal, so that we could interpret the eye movements in the best way also on the basis of the individuals' statements. After evaluating the heat maps, gaze plots and semantic differentials, it was possible to posit some data in terms of responses common to many of the individuals involved in the experiment (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Examples of the analysis results with eye tracking (heat maps) on the concept of the car seat.

Heat map is a graphic representation produced by the Eye-tracking instrument that shows the concentration of fixations in a specific area taking into account both the amount of the same and the time dedicated.

The data resulting from the analyses made with Eye-tracking and the semantic differential was compared with that drawn from the assessments previously made on the same materials with the Sensotact®: in most cases the evaluations were very similar, particularly with regard to the thermal perception and roughness of the materials, with the exception of the 3D fabrics.

Our analysis of the pictures, gaze plots and heat maps in particular, made it possible to formulate a number of considerations about the semantic differential item “beautiful/ugly” and “comfortable/uncomfortable”. For example the pictures that were found to be most closely observed by the individuals seem to be those rated positively in the semantic differential item “beautiful/ugly”; the individuals seemed tempted to allow their gaze to linger on the seats that they considered to be beautiful and comfortable (on these seats the thermal maps reveal red/yellow zones larger than on the other ones). The maps therefore show us that the observers do not focus their attention on a picture they consider uninteresting. Moreover by these analyses it is possible to consider that Eye-tracking could not be used as the only instrument to determine the characteristics of materials.

These considerations, in any case, require more probing verification: this experiment was limited by the small number of test individuals, and the excessively uniform cultural level of the group.

Furthermore, in case of future, more complete assessments of the project concept, the test will have to be repeated, after some time, with the same individuals to verify the results and establish whether and to what extent their perception of the images (which the individuals will have seen before) varies on a second analysis.

Moreover the pictures used during the tests can be characterised by a lower number of variables (colour, type of fabric/combinations of different fabrics/type of seat, proposed by degrees and not all together) and also supported by real samples of the materials.

In addition to the tactile characteristics, other properties of the materials can be analysed, such as the acoustic and visual properties and their eco-sustainability.

When used with a scientific method as an additional instrument for assessing meta-project or product concepts, or prototypes, Eye-tracking does not replace man as an evaluator, but reinforces or weakens judgments, anticipating what could be the indications of choice made by the public for whom the product is intended.

CASE STUDY 2: ANALYSIS OF CHOCOLATE PACKAGING, ASSESSMENT OF PERCEIVED SUSTAINABILITY

The next case study, focused on the analysis of the packaging of the chocolate bars, is taken from an existing parallel multi-disciplinary research of Politecnico di Torino, *Pollenzo Index environmental and economics design* (2009-2012) whose objective is to outline an evaluation index of social, environmental and economic sustainability of the food product. As part of this research, a specific task is focused upon analyzing food packaging, with the dual aim of outlining an evaluation system, based upon the functional, communicative and environmental performance that a type of packaging must satisfy throughout its entire life cycle (Allione, Petruccelli, 2011) and at the same time investigating how the various end users perceive the eco-sustainability performance of the analyzed packaging.

THE CHOCOLATE BAR PACKAGING: THE METHOD USED TO PERFORM THIS TYPE OF ANALYSIS

In order to analyze the chocolate packaging, it was decided to integrate the use of qualitative methodologies, supported by the eye tracking tool. The aim of the research was to understand the aspects of communication of the chocolate bar packaging and the specific elements related to it, such as perception of the elegance, cost, practicality and eco-sustainability of the product. Below (Figure 7) are indicated the specific objects of the study and there the graphical demonstration of the different research steps:

Figure 7. The object of the case study and the adopted steps of the ICS method

The first phase of the research (Figure 8) was dedicated to the introductory questionnaire through which we began to verify the candidates' general evaluation of the chocolate bar packaging, always taking account of the communicative elements of

interest for the research. The candidates were also asked to stylize the analyzed packaging, with the aim of identifying the aspects considered "topical" in relation to chocolate bars.

This initial step highlighted the aspects perceived as

CASE STUDY: ANALYSIS OF CHOCOLATE BAR PACKAGING PERCEPTION

INTRODUCTORY QUESTIONNAIRE RESULTS

STYLIZATION EXAMPLES

EYE-TRACKING: DIFFERENT ATTENTIVE FOCALIZATION

SEMANTIC DIFFERENTIALS ELABORATION

Figure 7. Figure 8. Analysis of chocolate packaging: examples of the main results obtained by adopting different tools/qualitative and analytical techniques.

relevant for the candidates in relation to the chocolate bars shown to them.

As the graphic shows (Figure 9), the requirements that seem to be most relevant for packaging of this nature relate to aspects of practicality and eco-sustainability. The aesthetic aspect and originality also appear to be significant features, while elements relating to robustness and durability seem less influential. Cognitive elements seem therefore to take precedence over affective aspects.

As the same time, through the desk analysis, the features of the packaging were investigated and examined. This was aimed at making an in-depth analysis of both the formal and structural aspects of the packaging, along with the communication used and the contents of the same.

We started to identify the “markers” of the chocolate bar packaging, i.e. those elements that contribute to rapid processing of the product and its content. In particular, it was possible to identify that the marks of environmental compatibility, information on ingredients, materials and some aspects of product communication were an essential contribution for the immediate and heuristic perception of packaging that could be defined as “sustainable”.

Subsequently, we proceeded to make our analysis using eye tracking, through which, alongside assessment of the main points of interest identified by the initial scanpaths, the interviewees were invited to concentrate on a series of “stimuli” provided by the researcher during the session. This was aimed at identifying the actual areas of packaging perception, such as elegance, practicality, cost, sustainability and the high quality of taste of the product itself.

The focus areas were tripartite, in order to understand both the perceptive path of chocolate bar packaging, and the actual areas of interest (Figure 9). The candidates’ choices enabled us to break down chocolate bar packaging, allowing an initial selection of the elements, which arouse the attention of the user in accordance with the stimulus provided.

Thereafter, the semantic differentials led to identification of similar or opposing trends in the semantic areas presented to the candidates. This allows us to infer which stimuli are immediately combined and which, on the other hand, appear to be in dichotomy.

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

Thanks to the contribution of these integrated techniques and the use of the eye tracking tool, it was possible to identify the areas which, at a perception level, lead to an immediate and positive combination (for example, we note good coherence between the perception of the elegance of the product which, if positive, is also linked to the goodness of the same), or which, on the other hand, appear to be in opposition and coexist badly within the same packaging (this is the case in the perception of eco-sustainability which seems to affect the aspects of elegance of the product and, consequently, also the perception of the ‘goodness’ of the same)

Taking account of the associative and dichotomous aspects of the packaging and the communicative effectiveness that can be affected by these, we take, as an example, the case of the Venchi chocolate bar, (Allione, Petrucci, 2011). From the results obtained from the evaluation of the three types of analysed packaging, the Venchi chocolate bar packaging was found to be the one which best satisfies environmental performance requirements. However, although it presented the best environmental performance (low material content, low value of embodied energy or CO2 emissions), this aspect of the product does not emerge from the data obtained during the analysis relating to the perception of sustainability.

The Venchi product was found to be the most efficient also as regards aspects of elegance and goodness of the product, while the other chocolate bars which, in their packaging, express sustainability more strongly, evoked the adverse effect; the question therefore spontaneously arose as to whether the concept of sustainability communicated in the packaging actually affected the perception of the goodness and elegance of the product itself.

These aspects of the research led to an initial reflection on the communication of aspects of sustainability on packaging: in future, it will be necessary to reduce the dichotomous opposition between sustainability and elegance. The results of this analysis may be useful for creating an appropriate perceptive path in the design of chocolate bar packaging.

CONCLUSIONS

The methodological approach presented comprises sensory and sustainability analysis of products and services. The various disciplines involved have recently made considerable progress, identifying instruments and methods that are able to provide ever more realistic, scientific and objective explanations of how we perceive the world.

By proposing new and original tools, this methodological approach can help designers to create products that satisfy the user's demand for perceived quality.

REFERENCES

- Allione, C, Petruccelli, L. (2011), *Sustainable food packaging: A case study of chocolate products*, Berlin: In Proceedings of LCM 2011 - Towards Life Cycle Sustainability, 5th International Conference on Life Cycle Management, 28-31 August, Berlin, Germany
- Ashby, M. (2009) *Materials and the environment: eco-informed material choice*. Oxford, UK: Butterworth-Heinemann Ltd – Elsevier.
- Baldwin, C. L. (2003) Neuroergonomics of Mental Workload: New Insights from the Convergence of Brain and Behaviour in Ergonomics Research. In: *Theories and Issues in Ergonomics*, Science, 4, pp. 132-141
- Casco C., Petrosini L., Oliveri M. (2007) *Neuroscienze: Esplorando il cervello*. Milano, Italy: Masson.
- De Giorgi C., Astolfi A., Buiatti E., Lerma B., Arato F., Dal Palù D. (2011) *SounBe*, TO2011A000089
- Farah M.J. (2000), *The Cognitive Neuroscience of Vision*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell.
- Germak, C. by (2008) *Man at the Centre of the Project. Design for a New Humanism*. Torino, Italy: Umberto Allemandi Editore.
- Gibson J. (1979), *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*, Boston, Usa: Houghton Mifflin Company; trad. it. Luccio R. (1999), *Un approccio ecologico alla percezione visiva*, Bologna, Italy: Il Mulino
- Johnson-Laird, P. (1993) *Modelli mentali*. Bologna, Italy: il Mulino.
- Kosslyn S.M., (1994), *Image and brain: The resolution of the imagery debate*. Cambridge, Ma, USA: MIT Press.
- Lerma B., De Giorgi C. (2011) *The Critical Exploration of Materials for the Design Project A Method of Analysis below the Levels of Consciousness*. DESIGN PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICES, Vol. 5, Issue 6, Illinois, USA: Common Ground Publishing LLC.
- Lerma, B., De Giorgi, C., Allione, C. (2011) *Design e materiali. Sensorialità_sostenibilità_progetto*. Milano, Italy: FrancoAngeli.
- Manzini, E., Vezzoli, C. (1998) *Lo sviluppo del prodotto sostenibile. I requisiti ambientali dei prodotti industriali*. Santarcangelo di Romagna (RN), Italy: Maggioli.
- Melgaard, M.C., Civille, G.V., Carr, B.T. (2007) *Sensory Evaluation Techniques*. Boca Raton, USA: CRC press.
- Muller H. J., Rabbitt P. M., (1989), "Reflexive and voluntary orienting of visual attention: Time course of activation and resistance to interruption", *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception & Performance*, 15, pp. 315-330.
- Norman, D. A. (1997) *La caffettiera del masochista. Psicopatologia degli oggetti quotidiani*. Milano, Italy: Giunti Editore.
- Pagliarini, E. (2002) *Valutazione sensoriale*. Milano, Italy: Hoepli.
- Ricci, C. (1980) *Il differenziale semantico: una proposta di revisione*. Milano, Italy: Vita Pensiero.
- Riccò, D. (1999) *Sinestesie per il design. Le interazioni sensoriali nell'epoca dei multimedia*. Milano, Italy: Etas.
- Rognoli, V., Levi, M. (2011) *Il senso dei materiali per il design*. Milano, Italy: FrancoAngeli.
- Tamborini P. (2009), *Design sostenibile. Oggetti, sistemi e comportamenti*. Milano, Italy: Mondadori Electa.
- Van Raaij, F.W. (1984), *Affective and Cognitive Reaction to Advertising*, Marketing Science Institute, report 84-111.
- Vannoni, D. (2009), *Gli oggetti nella mente la mente negli oggetti*, Novara, Italy: Utet.
- Vaughn, R (1986), *How Advertising Works: a Planning Model Revisited*, *Journal of Advertising Research*, February/March, pp. 57-66.